

MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract

The article touches upon one of the urgent problems of Russian higher education - the training of highly qualified specialists in the humanities. Due to the lack of curriculum time for the study of a foreign language by students of humanitarian specialties, teachers of higher education are trying to find ways to optimize the educational process and solve the problem of improving the methodology of teaching a foreign language.

This paper aims to consider the effective use of multimedia technologies in the educational process as one of the ways to solve this problem. The experience of the technique of combining traditional and new multimedia technologies is analyzed. It has made language learning more productive, effective, and communicative. In the process of teaching foreign languages using multimedia technologies, much attention is paid to the systematic and consistent work, the formation of students' personal interest and the desire to perform educational work at a high level.

Criteria for teaching a foreign language to students of a humanitarian profile using multimedia technologies were developed: target, content, motivational, effective criteria and optimality.

New approaches to the creation and use of multimedia technologies are proposed. The use of a criteria-based assessment and comparison of certain criteria and indicators, the application of the acquired knowledge corresponding to the levels of mastery of foreign languages (starter, elementary, pre-intermediate, intermediate, upper-intermediate, advanced) makes it possible to compare the effectiveness of using MMT in the educational process.

The introduction of multimedia into the learning process makes it possible to ensure a positive attitude towards the subject being studied, to increase interest and diversify the forms of learning. It is a good stimulus for learning, which improves the quality of students' knowledge, creates conditions for high-quality independent assimilation of the material and for the development of cognitive interest.

Keywords: education, foreign language, multimedia technology, computer training.

1 INTRODUCTION

The problem of training highly qualified humanitarian specialists is still relevant. In the context of a severe limitation of study time (1 - 2 classes per week), the best ways to solve problems for improving the methodology of the process of teaching a foreign language are looked for. In this context, the actual task is to improve the didactic theory of teaching foreign languages in relation to new educational conditions.

The characteristics of the experience of using multimedia technologies in teaching foreign languages showed that foreign teaching experience is far ahead of the domestic one, which confirms the need for this study. The analysis of the existing computer learning software in the field of foreign language teaching revealed that the selected didactic computer programs are adequate to the developed learning models.

The solution of the problem of optimizing the teaching of a foreign language to students of the humanities must be sought on the path of intensification and rational organization of the educational process. One of the ways to solve this problem, according to a number of domestic and foreign experts, is the use of multimedia technologies (MMT) in the educational process.

Analysis of scientific research [Gal'skova N.D., Gez N.I., 2013, Gritsenko L.I., 2013, Nurtdinova G.M. etc., 2022]. shows that, despite the significant progress that has been made recently in the implementation of various multimedia learning technologies, their potential is not realized in the educational process due to the lack of multimedia educational complexes, algorithms for their development and application, guidelines for their effective use in the process of teaching a foreign language.

2 METHODS

The purpose of this scientific study is to clarify the pedagogical essence, content and structure of the process of using multimedia technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language to humanitarian specialists in a university.

To achieve this goal, we used a complex methodology. It includes theoretical and empirical methods:

- theoretical methods - analysis of psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature on the research problem, study of educational and methodological documentation of Kazan State University (KFU) (training and educational programs, curricula and thematic plans).
- Empirical methods - a survey of foreign language teachers about changes that will help to improve the process of teaching a foreign language, the difficulties they experience, and the objective reasons for their occurrence; observation; visits to open and demonstration classes of teachers; conversations with teachers and students of KFU. [Diane Larsen-Freeman etc., 2008].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The limited time allocated by the governing documents for the study of a foreign language at the Kazan State University (qualification requirements, curricula and thematic plans) determines the need to use multimedia technologies in teaching humanitarian students.

Multimedia technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language to humanitarian students have a number of advantages. They help:

- to individualize and differentiate the learning process;
- to activate educational activity of students;
- to optimize the educational process itself;
- to increase the motivation of students and teaching staff;
- to create favorable conditions for independent work;
- to contribute to the development of self-esteem among students and teaching staff and create a comfortable learning environment [Mandel B. R., 2016].

Multimedia technologies for teaching a foreign language to humanitarian students allow using a computer at all stages of teaching a foreign language:

- stage of input of educational material,

- the stage of assimilation of educational information,
- the stage of repetition and consolidation of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities,
- stage of control [Gubaidullina R., Dorofeeva E., 2022].

An important feature of using a computer in teaching students a foreign language is that it can be a “interlocutor” of a student, i.e. work in a communicatively oriented dialog mode and in a certain way, for example, using graphic tools, a speech analyzer and synthesizer, make up for the lack of a natural communicator, modeling and imitating his verbal and non-verbal communication.

The computer makes it possible to obtain detailed information of a country-specific nature, about the features of the environment and the situation. It has great potential for constructing color and colorful images that can be transformed within the specified limits. With the help of a computer, one can easily explain various phenomena of language, speech, and speech activity. And all these explanations will be very active and productive [Shchukin A.N., 2015].

Unfortunately, most foreign language teachers with humanitarian education do not know how to use all the computer devices, and the thought of using a computer “monster” in all classes causes them only fear and irritation.

To solve the abovementioned tasks, we conducted oral and written surveys among English teachers of KFU, which revealed a high willingness of teachers to use information and communication technologies in teaching a foreign language. This is justified by the fact that KFU is an innovative university with an excellent information and communication environment (electronic scoreboards, MOODLE, Sanako, interactive whiteboards, a multimedia projector, accessible Internet, excellent linguistic laboratories, electronic textbooks and teaching aids).

However, traditional technologies remain in the pedagogical activity of foreign language teachers - the grammar-translation method (36%), game technologies are used by 31% of teachers, only 53% of teachers use multimedia technologies (video materials of a linguistic nature, multimedia presentations, project method, Internet testing, electronic teaching aids, electronic dictionaries and encyclopedias, listening texts, online testing, conducting a teleconference using webcams). It turned out that 30% of teachers and students are not satisfied with how and with the help of what technologies the educational process is organized. Wide range of teachers are poorly included in the process of studying advanced pedagogical experience, since they are practically not responsible for the quality of training of specialists and are little stimulated (morally and financially).

In KFU digital educational resource (DER) was developed - this is a teaching multimedia course (for each subject) designed for students of all specialities. The DER on foreign language contains: Language focus (a training course with rules and control exercises to consolidate them), Vocabulary, Pronunciation, Real life video (video and exercises to control understanding).

In the process of teaching foreign languages using multimedia technologies, much attention is paid to the systematic and consistent work, the formation of students' personal interest and the desire to perform educational work at a high level.

The computer program for the academic discipline "Foreign language" includes a hypertext computerized textbook. It includes a text part (grammar reference material), various training exercises and assignments, presentations of three types: on the basics of grammar, vocabulary building and development of communication skills, audio material with assignments, digital video films with assignments, a glossary, tests, a discipline curriculum and applications.

Computer tasks contained:

- question-answer dialogue;
- dialogue with selective answer;
- dialogue with a freely configurable response;
- exercises to fill in the blanks;
- exercises for self-control of vocabulary possession;

- text construction;
- work on pronunciation;
- exercises for matching;
- exercises to choose options;
- exercises to complete the crossword puzzle.

Exercises for self-control of vocabulary possession had various options:

- the computer offers a list of words for translation;
- the computer offers to correlate two lists of words (Russian and foreign) and find equivalent pairs of these words in both languages;
- the computer offers to correlate two lists of foreign words and establish pairs of synonyms or antonyms;
- the computer offers a list of foreign words and a list of definitions of these words (the student is required to connect each word with its corresponding definition). [Gubaidullina R., Dorofeeva E., 2022, O.A. Strelkova, O.Y. Ryauzova, 2020].

In addition, the hypertext computerized textbook contained a set of information support tools, a database, a test constructor, programs for controlling and monitoring knowledge in a foreign language and determining the level.

In the course of the study, criteria for teaching a foreign language to students of the humanities profile using MMT were developed: target, content, motivational, effective criteria and optimality. They reflect the specific features of the academic discipline "Foreign language" (intersubjectivity, multilevelness, multifunctionality). The author believes that these criteria are applicable in assessing the effectiveness of the use of MMT in universities. Each of the listed criteria has indicators presented in Table 1. The selected criteria and indicators of the pedagogical effectiveness of teaching a foreign language to students of the humanities with the use of MMT allow us to evaluate the effectiveness of using this technique [Verbitskii A.A., 2013].

Table 1: Criteria and indicators of the effectiveness of the use of MMT in teaching a foreign language to students of the humanities

Target	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - correspondence of the types of MMT to the development of foreign language competence of students of the humanitarian profile (speech, language, sociocultural, educational and cognitive); - place and role of MMT in educational material; - consistency and integrity of MMT use.
Informative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - compliance of the content of MMT facilities with the content of curricula and thematic plans, the study of topics aimed at developing professional communication skills (Careers in tourism, Destinations, Hotel facilities, Tour operators, dealing with guests, Travel agencies, Hotel reservations, Seeing the sights); - providing didactic assistance to students in in-depth and creative mastery of educational material in the process of planned classes and independent work.
Motivational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - development of motivation for learning a foreign language (communicative, social, operational-instrumental); - education of readiness for independent and continuous study of a foreign language; - student satisfaction with the learning process.

Productive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - satisfaction of the teacher with the results of their activities; - professional growth of the teacher in the development of new approaches; - the level of knowledge gained by students as a result of using MMT; - the ability to communicate freely in unprepared professional situations; - the formation of a sustainable interest in learning a foreign language.
Optimality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the quality of assimilation of knowledge by trainees, mastering the skills and abilities of professionally oriented foreign language communication; - formation of skills of all types of speech activity: speaking, writing, reading and listening; - independence and activity of students in educational activities; - the minimum necessary time spent to achieve the required results in teaching a foreign language.

The use of a criteria-based assessment and comparison of certain criteria and indicators, the application of the acquired knowledge corresponding to the levels of mastery of foreign languages (The use of a criteria-based assessment and comparison of certain criteria and indicators, the application of the acquired knowledge corresponding to the levels of mastery of foreign languages (starter, elementary, pre-intermediate, intermediate, upper-intermediate, advanced) makes it possible to compare the effectiveness of using MMT in the educational process.

4 SUMMARY

The necessary advantages of using MMT in the process of teaching a foreign language, the authors attributed: individualization and differentiation of learning; storage of sufficiently large amounts of information and the possibility of its transfer; easy access when the user accesses databases on each topic of the discipline "Foreign language"; the possibility of dialogue between the user and the computer; complex multisensory influence on various channels of perception (visual, auditory, kinesthetic) through the use of text, sound, animation, video; automating the process of solving tests on all topics and, as a result, organizing the management of educational activities and monitoring the results of assimilation of educational material on each topic and the course as a whole.

5 CONCLUSION

Technologization of the organization and content of the complex application of MMT in teaching a foreign language to students of a humanitarian profile in a university is one of the ways to improve it. The most significant organizational and pedagogical conditions for the implementation of this path in practice are providing the university with the necessary MMT, timely maintenance and repair of technical teaching aids, optimal planning of the use of MMT in the classroom, control over their use, and the introduction of a combined approach to the production of didactic materials.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

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